

Perceptions of Married Female Teachers Regarding the Impact of Job on their Family Life

Saima Zaman Khalil ¹ and Nida Gul ²

¹ Principal, University Model School, University of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

¹ B.Ed, Department of Education, University of Peshawar, Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

This article may be cited as Khalil, S. B., & Gul, N. (2023). Perceptions of Married Female Teachers Regarding the Impact of Job on their Family Life. *ProScholar Insights*, 2(1), 20-27. <https://doi.org/10.62997/psi.2023a.53308>

Abstract: The impact of job on the family life of married female teachers was the title of the research. The purpose of this study was to explore the impact of the job on the family life of married female teachers and to describe the perceptions of family members regarding married female jobs. The entire primary school teacher constituted the population for the study. A sample of 100 married female teachers from 34 schools was randomly selected for this study. A quantitative research design was used for which a five-point Likert-type rating scale consisting of 12 items was designed. Data was collected from the married female primary school teachers. Percentage was used as a statistical tool for analysis of the collected data. Based on the findings, it was concluded that half of the female teachers feel that they face problems in getting permission to teach. The majority of female teachers feel that the distance of school from home also lowered their job satisfaction level. Most of the participants believed teaching jobs cause differences among their husbands. Most of the female teachers were that they had enough time for their husbands.

Keywords: Family life, Job, Teaching, School Distance, Physical and Mental Health

Correspondence:

saimabasi43@gmail.com

Principal, University Model School,
University of Peshawar, Khyber
Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Introduction

Background of the Study

As female participation in labor increased significantly after the 1950s, long-held beliefs about the roles of family members—that is, that men should provide for the family's needs while women should take care of them—were called into question. Due to the tension between women's roles as employees and traditional home responsibilities, these changes in the labor force composition had an effect on family life. Married female employees received significant attention in the early phase of work-life study because their employment in the workforce went against their conventional role as a career in the family. Therefore, work-life research was first associated with married women and was a gendered phenomenon (Jayawardena & Seneviratne, 2003; Eby et al., 2005).

Although married women and couples with two incomes were the primary subjects of early research studies on work-family conflict, experts now understand that this problem transcends both gender and family dynamics. Regardless of a person's gender or marital situation, a large number of studies have worked to identify the causes, moderators, mediators, and consequences of work-family conflict over the past 20 years. Furthermore, the idea of work-life conflict, which focuses on life domains other than family and work alone, has replaced traditional perspectives on work-family conflict in contemporary studies in this field (Fisher et al., 2009; Hecht & McCarthy, 2010; Keeney et al., 2013; Daniel & Sonnentag, 2014).

Accordingly, studies have shown that a person's work-life conflict is influenced by a wide range of factors, including organizational characteristics, family-related factors, and individual differences. Due to the negative effects of their workers' poor work-life balance or work-family conflict, such as stress, absenteeism, burnout, and job and family unhappiness, employers' interest in improving their workers' work-life balance has also increased recently.

Researchers have been motivated by this to develop more potent therapies to help employees who are experiencing work-home (or overall life) conflict (Hammer et al., [2011](#)).

Prior to recently, the majority of research in this field was on the organizational level in an effort to provide organizational interventions like flexible work schedules and family-friendly benefits. Nonetheless, other academics have emphasized that, rather than occurring at the organizational level, work-life conflict is an individual-level phenomenon that is socially produced. Because each person is unique, they will, therefore, interpret work-life conflict in different ways (Kreiner et al., [2009](#)).

Work-family conflict refers to the inter-role conflict that arises when the demands of the work and family roles become mutually incompatible and where role pressures from the work domain interfere with the family domain and vice versa. The latest study, however, goes beyond this conventional viewpoint. Rather, it is expected that people will participate in a wide range of other areas of life besides job and family. Individuals also differ in how much weight they place on each of these life domains. Therefore, when a person's expectations for their work and other areas of their life conflict, work-life conflict results. In particular, when work adversely affects other areas of one's life, that individual may sense a work-life conflict. Community involvement, education, family, friendships, health, household management, leisure, and romantic connections are the eight common life domains. Finding out if personality factors influence the perceived conflict between work and each of these various life domains is the primary goal of this research (Keeney et al., [2013](#)).

Statement of the Problem

Prior knowledge of work-life imbalance is necessary because it facilitates a better understanding of the origins, causes, and repercussions of the imbalance—all of which make it easier to strike a balance. These days, deadlines are becoming more stringent, and it is the responsibility of the individual to deliver high-quality work while meeting deadlines. Maintaining a family life becomes incredibly tough as a result of this professional strain. The shift from work-life imbalance to work-life balance is clearly advantageous for all organizations and their staff. Achieving a work-life balance can significantly transform an individual's life and have a significant impact on society. The study under investigation is the perceptions of married female teachers regarding the impact of jobs on their family life.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives are put forward to construct the study.

1. To describe the perceptions of family members regarding married female teachers' jobs.
2. To explore the impact of a job on the family life of married female teachers

Research Questions

The following questions are developed to achieve aims and objectives.

1. What are the perceptions of family members regarding married female teachers' jobs?
2. What is the impact of the job on the family life of married female teachers?

Delimitations

The researcher delimited her study to married female teachers at public primary schools in the district of Swabi.

Review Of Related Literature

Numerous studies on the work-family balance of persons have been carried out by different researchers, and more studies are now being done on women (Kalsoom, [2021](#); Uddin, [2021](#); Adisa et al., [2021](#); Akanji et al., [2022](#); Kara et al., [2021](#)). Numerous factors were shown to have a good or negative impact on married working women's work-family balance, and these effects were observed to be more pronounced at this time. (Uddin, [2021](#); Kalsoom, [2021](#)). Due to the national lockdown and social isolation, the women experienced a worsening of their situation since they were

unable to receive assistance from family members, nursery facilities, housekeepers, or other sources (Uddin, 2021). While men's increases in housework hours were dependent on women's work patterns, which led to the layoffs and unemployment of their female coworkers, women's hours of housework and family responsibilities increased independently of men's work patterns (Andrew et al., [2020](#); Mussida & Patimo, [2021](#); Boca et al., [2020](#); Adisa et al., [2021](#)).

Women's stress levels have increased in certain countries due to deeply rooted patriarchal attitudes and confinement measures put in place to stop the spread of COVID-19. Their traditional gender norms and the stereotypical view that views men as "breadwinners" and women as "homemakers" were the cause of it (Akanji et al., [2022](#); Uddin, [2021](#)). Furthermore, role conflict brought on by teleworking during COVID-19 had a significant negative impact on working women. Women found it challenging to distinguish between their duties as a result of the coexistence of the roles of work and family. Such demands to meet both work and family duties are likely to affect the general health of women. Due to the loss of personal resources (time, energy, and money), there has been a rise in male chauvinism, health issues, and career stagnation (Kalsoom, [2021](#); Adisa et al., [2021](#)). However, some women's physical challenges as children or violent husbands made their mental health much worse (Kalsoom, [2021](#)).

The literature also demonstrates that as time goes on, there is an increasing proportion of males taking on domestic tasks. According to Andrew et al. ([2020](#)), although females continue to bear the majority of the responsibility for the significantly increased amount of time spent on childcare and housework, men are also making significant time contributions to family obligations. This is particularly true for married couples where the father has lost his work, and the mother has maintained hers. Fathers now handle slightly more than half of the childcare and housework in these households. Few studies have demonstrated that, despite a variety of challenges, "work from home" has been advantageous for certain people. Married working women have found it motivating since it has made it possible for them to reconcile job and family obligations, something they were unable to achieve in the past. The incentive stemmed from the fact that women could now spend more time with their families. This was because working people could spend more time with their families because they didn't have to spend as much time commuting to work (Adisa et al., [2021](#); Pedersen et al., [2009](#); Wu et al., [2022](#); Alhas, [2020](#)).

Additionally, people were compelled to spend more time with their families in order to receive social support due to the impact of the Covid-19 epidemic on social isolation and loneliness brought on by working from home. Furthermore, according to Pierce et al. ([2020](#)), changes in the educational system, job responsibilities, socioeconomic security, family time, and commuting time may result in reduced stress and an improvement in the mental health and well-being of some people. According to Adisa et al.'s research from 2021, there is a positive association between rising job and family duties, role conflict, close family values, and a decline in adolescent criminality and delinquency during the lockdown. They also emphasize how, for women, spending time by themselves at home has strengthened marriages, bonded families, and even increased parent-child intimacy—things that were previously hindered by the competing demands of paid employment and other extracurricular activities. The women found fulfillment in taking on several duties through multitasking, particularly when it came to the benefits of maintaining strong relationships with their family members and reviving traditional family values.

According to published research, married working women were disproportionately impacted by the shift in work patterns that occurred during the epidemic. It was vital to investigate these issues in order to make married women's lives better. The majority of the literature was quantitative in nature, and it lacked a thorough analysis to pinpoint the issues married working women faced. Another shortcoming of earlier research was its lack of attention to the situation of working women in third-world nations like Pakistan.

Research Methodology

A descriptive research approach was adopted in this study, and data was collected through a survey method using a questionnaire. The entire primary school teacher constituted the population for the study. The researcher's area of interest was a married female teacher in the desired population. A sample of 100 married female teachers from 34 schools was randomly selected for this study. A quantitative research design was used for which a five-point Likert-

type rating scale consisting of 12 items was designed. Data was collected from the married female primary school teachers. Percentage was used as a statistical tool for the analysis of the collected data.

Analysis of Data

Table 1

Items	Permission of teaching from family?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		20	30	10	20	20
Percentage		20%	30%	10%	20%	20%

Table 1 shows that 50% of female teachers feel that they have to face problems in getting permission for teaching.

Table 2

Items	Did you feel that the distance of schools from home affects your family life?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		40	45	5	5	5
Percentage		40%	45%	5%	5%	5%

Table 2 shows that 85% of female teachers feel the distance of school from home also lowered their job satisfaction level.

Table 3

Items	Did you feel that a teaching job affects your children's physical and mental health?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		30	20	10	20	20
Percentage		30%	20%	10%	10%	10%

Table 3 shows that 50% of female teachers feel that teaching also affects their physical and mental health levels.

Table 4

Items	Do you feel that with teaching, you are unable to give time to your children?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		50	40	0	5	5
Percentage		50%	40%	0%	5%	5%

Table 4 shows that 90% of female teachers feel that they are unable to give proper time to their children.

Table 5

Items	Do your family have wrong perceptions of your teaching job	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		50	30	0	10	10
Percentage		50%	30%	0%	10%	10%

Table 5 shows that 50% of female teachers agreed that there is a wrong perception of women's employment in our society.

Table 6

Items	Do you agree that a teaching job may cause differences between your family and husband?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		40	35	5	10	10
Percentage		40%	35%	5%	10%	10%

Table 6 shows that 75% of female teachers were of the opinion that teaching jobs cause differences between their husbands.

Table 7

Items	Do you have enough time for your husband?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		60	30	0	5	5
Percentage		60%	30%	0%	5%	5%

Table 7 shows that 90% of female teachers said that they had enough time for their husbands.

Table 8

Items	Do you feel that a teaching job creates a tense environment in your home?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		30	20	10	20	20
Percentage		30%	20%	10%	10%	10%

Table 8 shows that 50% of female teachers agreed with this statement.

Table 9

Items	Have you seen any married women whose life was so much affected by a teaching job?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		30	20	10	20	20
Percentage		30%	20%	10%	10%	10%

Table 9 shows that 50% of married females agreed to this item.

Table 10

Items	Do you have enough time for kitchen or household work with teaching?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		40	40	5	5	10
Percentage		40%	40%	5%	5%	10%

Table 10 shows 80% of female teachers that have enough time for household work.

Table 11

Items	Do you feel that a teaching job may cause tension and depression in your life?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		30	20	10	20	20
Percentage		30%	20%	10%	10%	10%

Table 11 shows that 50% of female teachers feel that teaching jobs cause tension and depression in their lives.

Table 12

Items	Suppose a choice is given between a teaching job and family. Did you choose family life?	SA	A	U	SDA	DA
Frequency		50	30	10	5	5
Percentage		50%	30%	10%	5%	5%

Table 12 shows that 80% of female teachers feel that they must choose a better family life.

Findings

1. Table 1 shows that 50% of female teachers feel that they have to face problems in getting permission to teach.
2. Table 2 shows that 85% of female teachers feel that the distance of school from home also lowered their job satisfaction level.
3. Table 3 shows that 50% of female teachers feel that teaching also affects their physical and mental health levels.
4. Table 4 shows that 90% of female teachers feel that they are unable to give proper time to their children.

5. Table 5 shows 50% of female teachers agreed that there is a wrong perception of women employment in our society.
6. Table 6 shows that 75% of female teachers were of the opinion that teaching job causes differences between their husband.
7. Table 7 shows that 90% of female teachers were that they have enough time for their husbands.
8. Table 8 shows that 50% of female teachers agreed with this statement.
9. Table 9 shows that 50% of married females agreed to this item.
10. Table 410 shows 80% of female teachers that have enough time for household work.
11. Table 11 shows that 50% of female teachers feel that teaching job caused tension and depression in their life
12. Table 12 shows that 80% of female teachers feel that they must choose a better family life.

Conclusion

Half of the female teachers feel that they have to face problems in getting permission to teach. The majority female teachers feel that the distance from school from home also lowered their job satisfaction level. Half of the participants feel that teaching also affects their physical and mental health levels. Most of the participants feel that they are unable to give proper time to their children. Half of the subjects agreed that there is a wrong perception of women employment in our society. Most of the participants were of the opinion that teaching jobs cause differences among their husbands. Most of the female teachers were that they had enough time for their husbands. Half of the participants agreed with this statement. Half of the married females agreed to this item. The majority of the subjects agreed that they have enough time for household work. Half of the female teachers feel that the teaching job caused tension and depression in their life. Most of the female teachers feel that they must choose their better family life.

Recommendations

1. The government may provide transport facilities to female teachers to decrease the burnout rate.
2. The government may give extra incentives to female teachers for motivation and encouragement.
3. An awareness campaign regarding the importance of female jobs in teaching cadres might be arranged to reduce the rigidity of family members.
4. The government may provide daycare center facilities for married female teachers.
5. The female teacher may be encouraged to join the teaching profession for the sake of their upcoming generations.

References

- Adisa, T. A., Aiyenitaju, O., & Adekoya, O. D. (2021). The work–family balance of British working women during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Work-Applied Management*, 13(2), 241–260. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jwam-07-2020-0036>
- Akanji, B., Mordi, C., Ajonbadi, H. A., & Adekoya, O. D. (2022). The impact of COVID-19 on the work–life balance of working mothers: evidence from Nigerian academics. *Personnel Review*, 52(3), 703–723. <https://doi.org/10.1108/pr-08-2020-0636>
- Andrew, A., Cattan, S., Dias, M. C., Farquharson, C., Kraftman, L., Krutikova, S., Phimister, A., & Sevilla, A. (2020). *How are mothers and fathers balancing work and family under lockdown?* <https://doi.org/10.1920/bn.ifs.2020.bn0290>
- Alhas, A. M. (2020, April 21). More ‘family time’ amid coronavirus isolation at home. <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/latest-on-coronavirus-outbreak/more-family-time-amid-coronavirus-isolation-at-home/1812529>
- Boca, D., Oggero, N., Profeta, P., & Rossi, M. (2020). Women’s and men’s work, housework, and childcare, before and during COVID-19. *Review of Economics of the Household*, 18(4), 1001-1017. <https://www.iza.org/publications/dp/13409/womens-work-housework-and-childcare-before-and-during-covid-19>
- Daniel, S., & Sonnentag, S. (2014). Work to non-work enrichment: The mediating roles of positive affect and positive work reflection. *Work & Stress*, 28(1), 49-66. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678373.2013.872706>
- Eby, L. T., Casper, W. J., Lockwood, A., Bordeaux, C., & Brinley, A. (2005). Work and family research in IO/OB: Content analysis and review of the literature (1980– 2002). *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 66(1), 124-197. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2003.11.003>
- Fisher, G. G., Bulger, C. A., & Smith, C. S. (2009). Beyond work and family: A measure of work/nonwork interference and enhancement. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 14(4), 441-456. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1037/a0016737>
- Hammer, L. B., Kossek, E. E., Anger, W. K., Bodner, T., & Zimmerman, K. L. (2011). Clarifying work–family intervention processes: The roles of work-family conflict and family-supportive supervisor behaviors. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 96(1), 134-150. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1037/a0020927>
- Hecht, T. D., & McCarthy, J. M. (2010). Coping with employee, family, and student roles: Evidence of dispositional conflict and facilitation tendencies. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 95(4), 631-647. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1037/a0019065>
- Jayawardena, D., & Seneviratne, P. (2003). Human Resource Management: a postmodern reading. Paper presented at the 9th International conference on Sri Lanka Studies, Matara, Sri Lanka.
- Kalsoom, Q. (2021). Covid-19: experiences of teaching-mothers in Pakistan. *Journal of Gender Studies*, 31(3), 390–402. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09589236.2021.1923464>
- Kara, S. B. K., Günes, D. Z., & Tüysüzer, B. S. (2021). Work-family conflict during working from home due to pandemic: A qualitative research on female teachers. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 13(1), 251- 273. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1108/IWAM-07-2020-0036>
- Keeney, J., Boyd, E. M., Sinha, R., Westring, A. F., & Ryan, A. M. (2013). From “work-family” to “work-life”: Broadening our conceptualization and measurement. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 82(3), 221-237. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2013.01.005>.
- Kreiner, G. E., Hollensbe, E. C., & Sheep, M. L. (2009). Balancing Borders and Bridges: Negotiating the Work-Home Interface via Boundary Work Tactics. *Academy of Management Journal*, 52(4), 704-730. <https://dx.doi.org/10.5465/amj.2009.43669916>
- Lonska, J., Mietule, I., Litavniece, L., Arbidane, I., Vanadzins, I., Matisane, L., & Paegle, L. (2021). Work–life balance of the employed population during the emergency situation of COVID-19 in Latvia. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.682459>
- Mussida, C., & Patimo, R. (2020). Women’s family care responsibilities, employment and health: A tale of two countries. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 42(3), 489-507. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10834-020-09742-4>

- Pedersen, D. E., Minnotte, K. L., Kiger, G., & Mannon, S. E. (2008). Workplace policy and environment, family role quality, and positive family-to-Work spillover. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 30(1), 80-89. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10834-008-9140-9>
- Pierce, M., Hope, H., Ford, T., Hatch, S., Hotopf, M., John, A., ... & Abel, K. M. (2020). Mental health before and during the COVID-19 pandemic: a longitudinal probability sample survey of the UK population. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(10), 883-892. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(20\)30308-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(20)30308-4)
- Uddin, M. (2021). Addressing work-life balance challenges of working women during COVID-19 in Bangladesh. *International Social Science Journal*, 71(239 –240), 7 –20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/issj.12267>
- Wu, H., Song, Q. C., Proctor, R. W., & Chen, Y. (2022). Family relationships under work from home: Exploring the role of adaptive processes. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.782217>

